

A RCT on Effectiveness of USG Guided Suprascapular Nerve Block Vs Landmark Guided Suprascapular Nerve Block for Adhesive Capsulitis Shoulder

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Abstract:

Background: Suprascapular nerve block (SSNB) is an effective method for the treatment of shoulder disorders. The present study was conducted to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of SSNB under ultrasonographic guidance with anatomical landmark-guided (LMG) technique in the treatment of adhesive capsulitis shoulder.

Objectives: To evaluate and compare the clinical and functional outcomes of ultrasound (US)-guided versus landmark-guided SSNB for the treatment of adhesive capsulitis shoulder.

Study design: Randomized, prospective analysis.

Setting: Patients attending Opd and casualty of department of orthopaedics of GMCH.

Materials and Methods: 500 patients with chronic shoulder pain and stiffness were enrolled. The patients were randomly allocated into 2 groups. 250 patients received US-guided SSNB with 5 ml of 0.75% ropivacaine and 250 underwent landmark-guided SSNB with same drug. Initial examinations before injection, first week and first and third months post injection were recorded. Visual Analog Scale (VAS) pain intensity levels, shoulder functions based on the Shoulder Pain and Disability Index (SPADI) were evaluated.

Results: Statistically significant recovery was observed in terms of VAS pain levels, SPADI from the first week after injection in both groups, but no significant difference was observed between the groups.

Discussion: In our study the techniques of the SSNB, i.e., USG and LMG resulted in decreased pain score, improved range of motion, and decreased SPADI scores after 3 months of administration of block. However, when both the techniques were compared with each other the improvement in pain score and shoulder movement and decrease in SPADI scores were comparable.

Conclusions: Our results indicate that US-guided SSNB does not potentially offer a significantly greater clinical improvement over landmark-guided SSNB in patients with adhesive capsulitis shoulder. However further research is required to establish this hypothesis in clinical practice.

Keywords: Chronic Shoulder Pain; Suprascapular Nerve Block; Ultrasound-Guided Suprascapular Nerve Block.

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Introduction

Chronic Shoulder pain is one of the most common chief complaints that is encountered in our clinic the cause of which can be several, resulting in functional disability and decline in quality of life. The first line of treatment for these patients consists of activity modification, physical therapy and analgesics. It is challenging to treat in a lot of patients because it does not respond well to conservative care causing a progressive reduction in movement that eventually results in adhesive capsulitis.[1]

This painful shoulder condition known as adhesive capsulitis is characterized by significantly restricted

ranges of motion, both passively and actively. The diagnosis is supported by the patient's gradual onset of pain and stiffness, loss of motion in all planes with increased pain at the extremes of motion and a history of thyroid or diabetes. Radiographs are usually negative and the diagnosis is discordant with osteoarthritis on radiography.[2] Failure of conservative therapy to treat such chronic shoulder pain necessitates interventional procedures like suprascapular nerve block (SSNB) which is safe and effective as well.[3][4]

Suprascapular nerve is a mixed nerve originating in upper trunk of brachial plexus, C5 and C6 roots

which provides two motor branches for supraspinatus muscle and three to four motor branches for infraspinatus muscle. The sensory components innervate the subacromial bursa, coracoclavicular ligament, and acromioclavicular articulation, in addition to the upper and posterior parts of the shoulder capsule. They supply 70% of the articulation sensitivity in the shoulder and axillary nerve branches supply the remaining. These delicate branches leave the suprascapular nerve both before and after they go beneath the superior transverse scapular ligament.[5]

Since Wertheim and Rovenstien introduced the surface landmark guided technique of SSNB in 1941, there have been a number of developments to the method.[3] The surface landmark guided technique of SSNB that is most often used is the one that Dangoisse et al. has described.[6]

Image guidance methods using computed tomography (CT), ultrasonography or fluoroscopy can increase the accuracy of surface landmark guided approaches. The benefit of ultrasound guidance is that it is a real-time process that allows one to see the drug's penetration around the suprascapular nerve (SSN) and recess site without exposing the patient or staff to radiation.[7]

There are few studies that compare the effectiveness of the landmark-guided (LMG) technique with the ultrasound-guided (USG) technique for the SSNB using ropivacaine 0.75% in treating adhesive capsulitis. Therefore, in order to compare and assess the surface landmark guided technique of SSNB with the USG guided technique of SSNB in patients diagnosed with adhesive capsulitis in terms of pain reduction, range of motion enhancement and shoulder function improvement, we have carried out this prospective study.

Materials and Methods

This prospective randomized study was conducted on patients attending in OPD and Casualty of Department of Orthopaedics, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital after the approval of Institutional Ethical Committee and with written informed consent from the patients for a period of 6 months from June 2023 to April 2024. The study included 500 patients who were referred to a physical medicine and rehabilitation outpatient clinic due to shoulder pain for longer than 3 months, of either gender, aged 18 years or over, with clinical diagnosis of adhesive capsulitis characterized by limitation of both active and passive Range of Motion of shoulder joint.

The patients with history of allergic reactions to Local Anaesthetics, Coagulopathy, receiving physical therapy for the shoulder region in the previous 6 months, receiving local injection to the shoulder

in the previous 3 months, with shoulder infection or a history of shoulder surgery, with septic/tuberculosis arthritis of the shoulder, uncontrolled diabetes or hypertension and patients not consenting for SSNB were excluded from the study. The patients were randomly divided in two groups of 250 each by a computer-generated randomized number table. Patients in Group A (n = 250) were given SSNB using the anatomical surface guided landmark technique described by Dangoisse et al.(1)(6) Patients in Group B (n=250) were given SSNB using the USG technique. Equal amounts of drug were given to both groups. In Group A, after all aseptic and anti-septic measures the nerve block was performed with patient in sitting position using a 21-gauge × 38 mm needle that was introduced through the skin, 2 cm cephalad to the midpoint of the spine of scapula. The needle was moved forward parallel to the scapular blade until it made bony contact with the suprascapular fossa floor. [1] After negative aspiration for blood, 5ml of 0.75% ropivacaine was slowly injected. Patients in Group B were given SSNB under ultrasound guidance with a SonoScape ultrasound equipment equipped with a linear probe of 6 to 13 MHz. The ultrasound probe was positioned in the coronal plane over the suprascapular fossa with a small anterior tilt while the patient was seated with their arm by their sides. In order to locate the SSN and artery on the fossa floor between the suprascapular notch and the spinoglenoid notch, the suprascapular fossa was scanned from the medial to the lateral side. Under the guidance of ultrasound, a 23-gauge Quincke spinal needle was used to puncture the skin in a mediolateral direction at an angle of 30-45 degrees to the vertical following local infiltration with a local anaesthetic solution. Following identification, a slow injection of 5ml of 0.75% ropivacaine was made under visualization into the region surrounding the nerve.[1][8]

The parameters used to determine the efficacy of SSNB were pain, range of motion and disability. The pain was assessed using VAS.(1) Prior to procedure the patients were acquainted with the use of VAS for the assessment of pain (where 0 denotes no pain and 10 is worst pain imaginable). Patients were asked to rate their pain at rest and after movement of the affected limb. The Shoulder Pain and Disability Index (SPADI), a self-administered questionnaire with two dimensions—one for pain and the other for functional activities—was used to assess disability. There are five questions in the pain dimension that ask about the intensity of a person's pain, and there are eight questions in the functional activities dimension that ask about how difficult it is for a person to perform different daily tasks that need using their upper extremities.[9]

Pain was measured before the procedure, at 30 minutes after procedure, after one week, after one

month and at 3 months after the SSNB, whereas SPADI was measured prior to the block, at one week, at one month and after three months following the procedure. Procedure-related adverse effects, including hematoma at the injection site, pleural puncture, vascular puncture, rash, itching, numbness, tingling, and paresthesia, were noted if present. All patients were given self-stretching exercises, active range of motion (ROM) exercises with stick assistance and finger ladders. The exercise program was showed by a physiotherapist.

Based on earlier studies, we assumed that the difference of 10 in SPADI scores between the two groups was considered clinically significant. At two-sided type 1 error of 4.5%, 95% confidence

interval, a sample size of 250 patients in each group was required to detect a significant difference. The statistical software for the social science system, version SPSS 17.0, was used to do statistical tests. Categorical data are shown as exact numbers and percentage, whereas continuous variables are shown as mean \pm SD.

Student's t-test was used to compare the normally distributed continuous variables between the groups, and paired t-tests were employed within Group I (LMG) and Group II (USG). When appropriate, Fisher's exact test or the Chi-squared test was used to compare nominal categorical data between the groups. It was deemed statistically significant when $P < 0.05$.

Figure 1: Sonoanatomy of suprascapular region. Pointer showing the target site where the suprascapular nerve runs with the suprascapular artery covered by fascia of supraspinatus muscle

Figure 2: Landmark Guided Suprascapular Nerve Block

Results: The data of all the 500 patients diagnosed with adhesive capsulitis of shoulder joint were analyzed. In both groups, the patient distribution with respect to age, sex, duration of pain was similar ($P > 0.05$).

Table 1:

	Group A	Group B
	Mean +/- SD	Mean +/- SD
Age (Years)	51.80 ± 10.55	53.80 ± 11.54
Gender n%		
Female	142	145
Male	108	105
Height (cm)	162.97 ± 8.64	163.20 ± 6.36
Weight (kg)	75.70 ± 17.12	75.90 ± 11.31
BMI (KG/m²)	28.47 ± 5.97	28.61 ± 4.60
Dominant hand %		
Right	83.30%	86.70%
Left	16.70%	13.30%
Affected shoulder %		
Right	73.30%	70%
Left	26.70%	30%
Shoulder pain duration (months)	25.16 ± 15.62	29.03 ± 21.72

Table 2:

	Vas Score At Rest			Vas Score With Activity		
	Group A	Group B	P Value	Group A	Group B	P Value
Baseline	3.1±2.1	3.37±1.6	>0.05	7.09±2.11	6.84±1.73	>0.05
After Block	2.8±0.97	2.76±1.3	>0.05	6.8±1.86	6.4±1.54	>0.05
1st Week	2.2±1.2	1.97±0.8	>0.05	4.87±2.39	4.2±1.97	>0.05
1st Month	1.92±0.87	1.65±0.77	>0.05	3.47±2.16	3.63±2.14	>0.05
3rd Month	1.71±0.9	1.45±0.6	>0.05	3.33±2.12	3.13±1.96	>0.05

Table 3:

SPADI			
	Group A	Group B	P Value
Baseline	69.39±20.85	65.48±16.66	>0.05
1st Week	38.20±23.97	29.44±13.32	<0.01
1st Month	28.97±19.5	23.72±14.9	>0.05
3rd Month	26.28±21.43	21.99±14.17	>0.05

Figure 3: VAS at rest

Figure 4: VAS at activity

Figure 5: SPADI

In Group A VAS for pain (at rest) decreased from 3.10 ± 2.1 at baseline to 2.80 ± 0.97 immediately after block. It further decreased to 2.20 ± 1.20 at 1st week, 1.92 ± 0.87 at 1st month, 1.71 ± 0.90 at 3rd month. Similarly, VAS for pain (at activity) decreased from 7.09 ± 2.11 at baseline to 6.80 ± 1.86 immediately after block. It further decreased to 4.87 ± 2.39 at 1st week, 3.47 ± 2.16 at 1st month, 3.33 ± 2.12 at 3rd month.

In Group B VAS for pain (at rest) decreased from 3.37 ± 1.6 at baseline to 2.76 ± 1.30 immediately after block. It further decreased to 1.97 ± 0.8 at 1st week, 1.65 ± 0.77 at 1st month, 1.45 ± 0.60 at 3rd month. Similarly, VAS for pain (at activity) decreased from 6.84 ± 1.73 at baseline to 6.40 ± 1.54 immediately after block. It further decreased to 4.2 ± 1.97 at 1st week, 3.63 ± 2.14 at 1st month, 3.13 ± 1.96 at 3rd month.

Mean SPADI score in Group A improved from baseline value of 69.39 ± 20.85 to 38.20 ± 23.97 at 1st week, to 28.97 ± 19.5 at 1st month, to 26.28 ± 21.43 at 3rd month. In Group B mean SPADI score improved from baseline value of 65.48 ± 16.60 to 29.44 ± 13.32 at 1st week, to 23.72 ± 14.9 at 1st month, to 21.99 ± 14.17 at 3rd month. When

compared to the baseline value, the VAS reduction in both groups was found to be statistically significant ($P < 0.001$) immediately following the block, one week later, 1 month and 3 months later. There was significant ($P < 0.001$) improvement in the SPADI at 1st week, 1 month and 3 months later after SSNB in both the groups.

There were no statistically significant differences between the two groups in VAS score and SPADI score before the procedure ($P > 0.05$). The VAS score of the two groups were statistically comparable with each other immediately after the block, at 1st week, at 1st month and at 3rd month following the block.

The USG group showed significantly better SPADI score than landmark guided group (P value < 0.05) at 1st week. The SPADI score at 1st month and 3rd month in both the group were statistically comparable (P value > 0.05). One patient in the Group B complained transient vagal symptoms which improved after sometime and did not require any intervention. No complications were observed in group A. The occurrence of complications in both the groups was statistically comparable (P value > 0.05).

Figure 6:

Figure 7: Case 1: At base line, patient is planned for land mark guided block (left side affected)

Figure 8:

Figure 9: Follow up at 3 months post land mark guided block

Figure 10: Case 2: at base line, patient is planned for USG guided block (right sided affected)

Figure 11:

Figure 12: Follow up at 3 months USG guided block

Discussion

SSNB is an easy-to-use, safe, and efficient treatment method that can be used in the outpatient department to relieve persistent shoulder pain. After four weeks of block delivery in our study, both the USG and LMG SSNB methods led to lower pain scores, better range of motion, and decreased SPADI scores. Nevertheless, the improvement in shoulder mobility and pain score as well as the drop in SPADI scores were similar when the two approaches were compared to one another.

With the exception of USG method, which at one week showed a notable improvement in shoulder function (i.e., much lower SPADI scores), however none of them turned out to be superior to the other.

The use of SSNB for postoperative analgesia following shoulder surgery and for the management of both acute and chronic shoulder pain is growing. Additionally, SSNB is favoured over alternative

treatment methods including intraarticular steroid injections and anti-inflammatory medications, both of which have drawbacks when used on the older population with multiple comorbidities like diabetes and renal impairment.[10–13]

The SSN is mixed nerve, possessing both motor and sensory fibers, accounting for 70% of sensory supply to the shoulder joint, mainly the posterior and superior capsule. It originates from the ventral rami of the fifth and sixth cervical nerve roots. It emerges from the lateral aspect of the upper trunk of the brachial plexus, then courses posteriorly and laterally to the scapular notch. It enters the supraspinous fossa through the suprascapular notch below the superior transverse scapular ligament. The suprascapular artery and vein pass above this ligament. In the supraspinous fossa, the nerve is in direct contact with bone and exits the suprascapular fossa to infrascapular fossa lateral to the spinoglenoid notch. The superior articular branch given off

in the supraspinous fossa, provides sensory supply to the coracoclavicular, coracohumeral ligaments, the acromioclavicular joint, glenohumeral joint, and subacromial bursa. SSN also gives off motor branches for the supraspinatus and the infraspinatus muscle.[14–17]

It is crucial to understand the anatomical features of the SSN since it is targeted in the suprascapular notch (posterior approach) or the supraspinous fossa (superior approach) to impede sensory impulses. The needle is guided into the notch via posterior approach techniques, which may not be present in 15% of individuals. This can lead to a pneumothorax because the needle's track is toward the thoracic cavity. However, since the supraspinatus muscle originates in the medial half of the fossa, superior method does not require the identification of the nerve; instead, the needle is inserted in the lateral half. This technique's benefits include a very low risk of pneumothorax, simplicity of access, and the lack of a need to identify the notch.[14] Dangoisse et al.'s landmark guide methodology is a superior method.[6] Image guidance methods including fluoroscopy, CT and more recently ultrasound have been employed to increase the precision of LMG treatments.

Harmon and Hearty published the initial description of the USG SSNB approach in 2007. They proposed that the transverse ligament and suprascapular notch represented the suprascapular region relevant to the SSN block on ultrasonography. The notch was the desired target of the ultrasound-guided injection.[18] Subsequently, a cadaveric and fluoroscopic investigation by Peng et al. recommended reinterpreting sonoanatomy. The SSN was seen on the floor of the scapular spine between the scapular notch and the spinoglenoid notch when the US probe was positioned in the coronal plane over the suprascapular fossa with a slight anterior tilt.

The fascia of the supraspinatus muscle was mistakenly identified as the transverse scapular ligament and the concave contour of the floor as the suprascapular notch. The suprascapular fossa, where it forms a compartment, was the target site for the SSN block, and the final needle-tip position was away from the notch, potentially reducing the danger of pneumothorax or local anesthetic spreading toward the brachial plexus.[19] Hence, the superior approach LMG techniques and the USG technique target the nerve in the same area. Shanahan et al. conducted a study to compare anatomical landmark approach of SSNB versus CT guided SSNB for shoulder pain in patients with degenerative joint rotator cuff disease. The patients were reviewed at 1, 4, and 12 weeks after injection. Similar to our findings, they observed that there were no significant differences in the improvement in pain and disability between the two approaches at any times.

The study concluded that CT guided and landmark approaches to performing SSNBs result in similar significant and prolonged pain and disability reductions and both approaches are safe.[20]

Our results are also in consensus to study by Arcila Lotero et al. who evaluated the clinical efficacy and safety of ultrasound guided SSNB in patients with chronic shoulder pain Following USG guided SSNB, they saw a considerable improvement in VAS score. In their investigation, 78.3% and 48.7% of patients reported having less pain two days and one month following the treatment, respectively.[21]

Ozkan et al. treated the Patients with diabetes mellitus and frozen shoulder who did not respond to intraarticular steroid injections, with SSNB under fluoroscopic guidance using a nerve stimulator needle.[22]

Gorthi et al. conducted a prospective randomized case-control study in fifty patients with perisoulder pain to analyze the effectiveness of SSNB under ultrasonographic guidance. Patients in the study group (n = 25) underwent nerve block with ultrasound guidance, whereas a control group (n = 25) of patients received the nerve block utilizing Moore's method without ultrasound guidance. VAS is used to measure the degree of pain, and the constant shoulder score (CSS) is used to assess shoulder function. They found that, in contrast to our findings, at the one-month follow-up, the study group had superior VAS and CSS patterns than the control groups ($P < 0.05$). The study group did not have any complications. However, in the control group there were two cases of arterial punctures and three instances of direct nerve injury with neurological deficit for 2 months.[23] The difference in results can be attributed to the Moore's technique of LMG SSNB used by them which targets the nerve in the suprascapular notch [24] while LMG technique used by us blocks the nerve in the supraspinous fossa.

The probable reason for similar result in both the groups may have been caused by the volume we utilized, 5 ml, which was adequate to fill each patient's lateral suprascapular fossa. In a study using cadavers, by Feigl et al. found that a volume of 5 ml is sufficient to fill in the lateral half of the suprascapular fossa. [25] A lower dosage could have led to different outcomes; for example, the USG group might have performed better since more precise injections are administered under supervision.

The limitation of the present study is mainly due to the short-term follow-up of patients after the block, so the long-term outcomes of both procedures could not be investigated in this study. A small sample size was another drawback; a larger sample size would have enabled us to more strongly validate our findings.

Conclusion

Both the procedures, USG guided SSNBs and the anatomical LMG guided ssnb described by Dangoisse et al. are effective and safe ways to treat adhesive capsulitis of shoulder. They enhance shoulder functioning, improve range of motion, and reduce shoulder pain. Both the procedures used in this study were comparable, with the exception that the USG group experienced an early improvement in shoulder function. More research is necessary to assess USG SSNB and compare it to other LMG techniques of SSNB, as there have been few studies evaluating it for the treatment of adhesive capsulitis of shoulder.

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